

Determinants of Women's Voices in Household Decision-Making Process in Indian Society: A Cross-sectional Analysis using NFHS-5 Data

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Abstract: Women's household decision-making reflects their empowerment and status in patriarchal societies like India. Despite various programmes, ever-married young women lack autonomy in key decisions. This study examines young ever-married women's decision-making in healthcare, purchases, mobility, and finances, and explores key socio-cultural and economic influencing factors. This study focused only 26,982 young currently married women who has response to household decision-making autonomy questions during NFHS-5. Among 26,982 young married women in India, 87.1% participate in household decisions, however 12.9% remain excluded, highlighting persistent gender disparities in household autonomy. The findings emphasize that higher education, media exposure, economic engagement, and progressive attitudes in partners significantly influence women's participation in household decisions. Overall, binary logistic analysis reveals that factors such as a woman's age, education level, occupation status, employment status, and her husband's alcohol consumption behaviour significantly influence her likelihood of participating in household decision-making independently. Empowering women through education, employment, media exposure, and reducing IPV could be key strategies to enhance their participation in household decision-making.

Keywords: Household, Decision-making, autonomy, ever-married, young women

Background: Women's empowerment and autonomy in decision-making are central to the discourse on gender equality and sustainable development. In patriarchal societies like India, the household often serves as a microcosm of broader gender dynamics, where women's participation in decisions regarding their own lives and family affairs reflects their overall status and agency. Household decision-making is not only a marker of gender equality but also an indicator of broader socio-economic development (Kabeer, 1999). Empowered women tend to have better health outcomes, increased educational attainment, and improved economic participation, contributing positively to the well-being of their families and communities (Jeejeebhoy, 2000; Bloom et al., 2001).

Despite significant strides in gender development, Indian women-particularly young, ever-married women-often continue to have limited autonomy in decisions related to their health, finances, and mobility. The intersection of traditional norms, educational attainment, caste, religion, and regional disparities shapes women lived experiences and influences their decision-making capacity. Understanding these structural determinants is vital for designing targeted interventions to promote gender equity and women's empowerment.

Rationale of the Study: Indian Government and various international agencies have launched programs promoting women's empowerment, including Beti Bachao

Beti Padhao, National Policy for Women, and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG-5). However, empirical evidence suggests that many Indian women still lack an active role in crucial household decisions. A significant proportion of women across states still report little or no say in decisions concerning their health care, household purchases, and financial matters. Young ever-married women, aged 15–29 years, represent a particularly important demographic. This life stage is often marked by transitions—marriage, childbirth, and household responsibilities—which can greatly affect their agency. However, this group is often understudied in national discourses on empowerment. Their ability to influence household decision-making can be a vital indicator of emerging patterns of gender equity in Indian society.

Significance of the Study: Understanding the determinants of women's decision-making is crucial for advancing gender equality and informing policies aimed at social development. By focusing on a nationally representative dataset from NFHS-5, this study offers updated insights into the socio-economic conditions that shape women's voices in private domains. The findings can contribute to academic literature on gender studies, sociology, and public policy while providing practical implications for stakeholders involved in women's welfare and development in India. Moreover, the study emphasizes that empowerment is a multidimensional phenomenon influenced not only by individual attributes but also by household, community, and cultural contexts. Disaggregating these layers through quantitative analysis provides a deeper understanding of where interventions can be most effective.

Objectives of the Study: This study aims to examine the extent of young ever-married women's participation in household decision-making across four key domains: personal healthcare, major household purchases, visits to family or relatives, and decisions regarding their husband's earnings. Further, the study identifies the socio-cultural, demographic and economic factors that influence women's participation in decision-making using nationally representative data.

Data source: Data retrieved from the nationwide comprehensive National Family Health Survey (V) conducted in 2019–2021. The NFHS-5 sample was designed as a stratified two-stage sampling approach, using the 2011 Census as the sampling frame. In rural areas, villages served as the Primary Sampling Units (PSUs), while in urban areas, Census Enumeration Blocks (CEBs) were used. PSUs were selected using a probability proportional to size (PPS) systematic sampling method. A detailed account of the survey methodology and sampling strategy can be found in the NFHS-5 report (IIPS). NFHS-5 interviewed totally 7,24,115 ever-married women aged 15 to 49 from 28 states and 8 Union Territories. It provides information on women's health, socio-economic, demographic background, empowerment status, and domestic violence. Of these women, this study focused only 26,982 young currently married women who has response to household decision-making autonomy questions.

Dependent variable: The decision-making status of ever-married young women aged 15 to 29 was considered as dependent variable in this study. It is constructed based on their participation in four important household decision-making areas: (1) decisions regarding their own healthcare, (2) major household purchases, (3) visits to their family or relatives, and (4) decisions on how to utilize their husband's earnings. Women's participation was categorized as independent, joint (with their husbands), or

dependent. The responses were recoded into a binary variable: responses indicating "not making the decision" were coded as '0', while those indicating the woman makes the decision either alone or jointly with her husband or someone else were coded as '1'.

Independent variables: This study aims to examine the relationship between decision-making and various background characteristics among ever-married young women in India, using a set of key socio-economic and demographic variables. These variables were selected and included based on insights from previous studies, with the objective of conducting a more in-depth analysis through the logistic regression model.

These variables include 'age group of the respondent (15-19, 20-24, and 25-29)', 'place of residence (Urban, Rural)' 'religion (Hindu, Muslim, Christian, Others)', 'caste group affiliation (Schedule tribe ST, Schedule caste SC, Other backward class OBC, FC, and Others)', 'educational attainment of wife and husband (No education, primary, Secondary, Higher)', 'respondent's current working status (Not working, working in agri. sector and Non-agri sector)' 'wealth index (Poorest, Poorer, Middle, Richer, Richest)', respondent's exposure to mass media (no exposure, less exposure, more exposure), 'marital duration (0-4, 5-9 and above 10 years)' 'husband's or partner's alcohol consumption habits (No, Yes)', and 'geographical region (North, Central, East, Northeast, West, South)'.

Data analysis Descriptive statistics is applied to understand the background characteristics of ever-married young women aged 15-29 in India. Further, a chi-square (χ^2) analysis is conducted to assess the association between the outcome variable and various exposure variables. This chi-square analysis helps to identify and exclude variables that are not statistically significant, retaining only those with a p-value less than 0.05 for inclusion in the binary logistic regression analysis (makes decision alone and/or jointly & not involving in the decision-making). The results of the binary logistic regression model are presented as odds ratios (OR) along with their corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CI). The analysis of the raw data was conducted using SPSS statistical software.

Table 1. Percentage of Young Women involved in Different HH decisions in India

Person who decides	Decision taken by		Total
	wife and/or husband	other than wife	
Wife's healthcare	78.1	21.9	27288
Major household purchases	74.9	25.1	27288
Visits to their family or relatives	77.5	22.5	27288
Utilize husband's earnings	73.1	26.9	26982
Overall HH decision	87.1	12.9	26982

Results: Table 1 discloses the percentage of women involved in different household decisions. Among the 26,982 currently married young women aged 15 to 29 in India, a promising 87.1% participate in at least one aspect of household decision-making, either independently or in collaboration with their husbands. However, 12.9% women entirely excluded from such decision-making processes. Overall, the data suggests that while a significant proportion of women participate jointly in decision-making with their husbands, a notable share still lack involvement-especially in financial matters such as the use of the husband's earnings. This indicates continued gender-based disparities in

autonomy within households. Notably, this highlights a significant gap in women's autonomy within the household context.

Table 2 presents the background characteristics of the study sample and presents the distribution of household decision-making participation among ever-married young women in India across various socio-economic and demographic characteristics. The chi-square test results indicate statistically significant associations for most variables with women's involvement in household decision-making. It is observed that the percentage women involved in HH decision-making increases with age of the women. Women aged 25–29 show the highest involvement (88.9%), compared to 80.8% among those aged 15–19 ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2. Socio-economic and demographic profile of Respondents and percentage of women involvement in HH decision making across background characteristics

Background Characteristics	Number	%	Decided by wife and with Husband	Decided by others	Chi-Square
AGE					
15-19	1951	7.2	80.8	19.2	.000 12.502
20-24	10151	37.6	85.8	14.2	
25-29	14880	55.1	88.9	11.1	
RESIDENCE					
Urban	5509	20.4	88.5	11.5	.001 11.588
Rural	21473	79.6	86.8	13.2	
Education					
No education	4164	15.4	84.5	15.5	.000 67.304
Primary	3200	11.9	87.0	13.0	
Secondary	15575	57.7	87.0	13.0	
Higher	4043	15.0	90.5	9.5	
RELIGION					
Hindu	20734	76.8	86.9	13.1	.000 52.909
Muslim	3654	13.5	85.3	14.7	
Christian	1534	5.7	92.3	7.7	
Others	1060	3.9	89.4	10.6	
CASTE					
SC	5509	20.4	86.0	14.0	.000 42.315
ST	4892	18.1	89.7	10.3	
OBC	10740	39.8	86.5	13.5	
FC	4310	16.0	87.7	12.3	
Others	1531	5.7	85.6	14.4	
WEALTH INDEX					
Poor	12546	46.5	87.0	13.0	NS
Middle	5753	21.3	86.7	13.3	
Rich	8683	32.2	87.6	12.4	
OCCUPATION					
Not working	20688	76.7	86.3	13.7	.000 59.663
Non-Agriculture	2877	10.7	91.1	8.9	

Agriculture	3417	12.7	88.6	11.4	
HUSBAND EDU.					
No education	3112	11.5	84.7	15.3	.000 22.104
Primary	3206	11.9	87.3	12.7	
Secondary	15923	59.0	87.2	12.8	
Higher	4741	17.6	88.2	11.8	
HUSBAND AGE					
15-24	4100	15.2	83.3	16.7	.000 64.132
25-39	22199	82.3	87.8	12.2	
40-59	656	2.4	87.7	12.3	
60+	27	0.1	81.5	18.5	
MARITAL DURATION					
0-4	12418	46.0	85.4	14.6	.000 63.592
5-9	10258	38.1	88.6	11.4	
10-19	4279	15.9	88.6	11.4	
MASS MEDIA					
Not exposed	6878	25.5	84.4	15.6	.000 75.043
Exposed to any one	11948	44.3	87.4	12.6	
Exposed to two or three	8156	30.2	89.1	10.9	
CEB					
No Child	5227	19.4	84.5	15.5	.000 47.708
One Child	8844	32.8	87.2	12.8	
Two Children	8616	31.9	88.5	11.5	
2+ Children	4295	15.9	87.4	12.6	
HUS. ALCOHOL					
Not having habit	15155	75.1	87.5	12.5	.006 6.336
Consuming alcohol	5024	24.9	88.9	11.1	
HUS. ATTITUDE					
High opinion	10885	53.8	89.4	10.6	.000 77.410
Moderate	5874	29.1	87.4	12.6	
Low opinion	3450	17.1	83.8	16.2	
IPV					
No IPV	14622	72.5	88.9	11.1	.000 58.054
Any form of IPV	5557	27.5	85.0	15.0	
REGIONS					
North	5034	18.7	86.1	13.9	.000 88.671
Central	6469	24.0	85.9	14.1	
East	5324	19.7	87.1	12.9	
North East	3641	13.5	91.5	8.5	
West	2647	9.8	88.4	11.6	
South	3867	14.3	85.5	14.5	

Urban women exhibit slightly greater involvement (88.5%) than their rural counterparts (86.8%; $p < 0.01$). Urban women exhibit slightly greater involvement (88.5%) than their rural counterparts (86.8%; $p < 0.01$). Women's decision-making power rises with education level. Those with higher education report the highest involvement (90.5%),

while uneducated women report the lowest (84.5%; $p < 0.001$). Christian women report the highest decision-making participation (92.3%), while Muslim and Hindu women report lower rates (85.3% and 86.9%, respectively) ($p < 0.001$). ST women report higher participation (89.7%), whereas SC women show lower involvement (86.0%; $p < 0.001$). Working women, particularly those in non-agricultural jobs, demonstrate significantly greater decision-making (91.1%) compared to those not working (86.3%; $p < 0.001$). Higher husband education is associated with greater female decision-making. Women whose husbands have higher education show 88.2% involvement ($p < 0.001$). Decision-making participation increases with marital duration, with those married for 10–19 years showing the highest rates (88.6%; $p < 0.001$). Women with greater exposure to mass media are more empowered in decision-making—89.1% for those exposed to two or more sources versus 84.4% for those not exposed ($p < 0.001$). Women whose husbands consume alcohol show slightly higher involvement (88.9%) compared to those whose husbands do not (87.5%; $p < 0.01$). Women whose husbands have a high opinion against wife-beating are more likely to participate in decision-making (89.4%) than those whose husbands hold a low opinion (83.8%; $p < 0.001$). Women not exposed to IPV are more involved (88.9%) compared to those who experienced any form of IPV (85.0%; $p < 0.001$). Regional variation exists, with the North-East showing the highest female involvement in decisions (91.5%), and the Central and South regions reporting relatively lower participation ($p < 0.001$).

Logistic regression models were constructed using all statistically significant variables, with decision-making as the dependent variable (0= Wife not involved in HH decision; 1= Wife independently and dependently involved in HH decision). Table 2 presents both unadjusted and adjusted odds ratios derived from the binary logistic regression model. An odds ratio (OR) greater than 1 indicates an increased likelihood of decision-making autonomy among young married women, an OR less than 1 suggests a decreased likelihood, and an OR equal to 1 denotes no association between the exposure and the outcome. Table 3 presents the results of the binary logistic regression analysis examining the predictors of decision-making autonomy among young married women in India. The model includes both individual and household-level variables and reports both the unstandardized regression coefficients (B) and odds ratios (Exp(B)), along with their 95% confidence intervals.

Table3: Binary regression model for decision-making among young married women in India

Background Variables	B	S.E.	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95.0% C.I. for EXP(B)	
						Lower	Upper
AGE **							
15-19 (Ref.)			2	.004	1.000		
20-24	.264	.092	1	.004	1.303	1.087	1.562
25-29	.333	.100	1	.001	1.396	1.148	1.696
RESIDENCE *							
Urban (Ref.)					1.000		
Rural	-.143	.059	1	.015	.866	.771	.973
EDUCATION ***							

No education (Ref.)			3	.000	1.000		
Primary	.110	.082	1	.177	1.116	.952	1.310
Secondary	.095	.068	1	.163	1.100	.962	1.257
Higher	.495	.104	1	.000	1.641	1.338	2.013
RELIGION							
Hindu (Ref.)			3	.862	1.000		
Muslim	.008	.070	1	.909	1.008	.879	1.156
Christian	.075	.131	1	.566	1.078	.834	1.394
Others	.088	.124	1	.479	1.092	.856	1.394
CASTE **							
SC (Ref.)			4	.010	1.000		
ST	.160	.077	1	.039	1.173	1.008	1.365
OBC	.037	.059	1	.533	1.038	.924	1.165
FC	.024	.076	1	.753	1.024	.882	1.189
Others	-.238	.108	1	.028	.788	.638	.974
OCCUPATION ***							
Not working (Ref.)			2	.000	1.000		
Non-Agriculture	.424	.082	1	.000	1.528	1.302	1.793
Agriculture	.229	.071	1	.001	1.257	1.094	1.444
HUSBAND EDU.							
No education (Ref.)			3	.226	1.000		
Primary	.131	.086	1	.129	1.140	.963	1.351
Secondary	.081	.072	1	.262	1.085	.941	1.250
Higher	-.016	.096	1	.866	.984	.816	1.187
MARITAL DURATION ***							
0-4 (Ref.)			2	.000	1.000		
5-9	.227	.056	1	.000	1.255	1.126	1.400
10-19	.254	.077	1	.001	1.290	1.110	1.499
MASS MEDIA ***							
Not exposed (Ref.)			2	.000	1.000		
Exposed to any one	.267	.055	1	.000	1.306	1.172	1.454
Exposed to two or three	.377	.067	1	.000	1.458	1.278	1.662
HUS. ALCOHOL ***							
Not having habit (Ref.)					1.000		
Consuming alcohol	.154	.055	1	.006	1.166	1.046	1.300
HUS. ATTITUDE TOWARDS WIFE-BEATING***							
High opinion (Ref.)			2	.000	1.000		
Moderate	-.112	.052	1	.033	.894	.807	.991
Low opinion	-.345	.061	1	.000	.708	.628	.799
IPV ***							
No IPV (Ref.)					1.000		
Any form of IPV	-.288	.052	1	.000	.750	.678	.830
REGIONS***							
North (Ref.)			5	.000	1.000		

Central	.208	.069	1	.002	1.232	1.076	1.410
East	.362	.073	1	.000	1.437	1.245	1.658
North East	.629	.098	1	.000	1.875	1.549	2.270
West	.191	.089	1	.031	1.211	1.017	1.441
South	-.112	.077	1	.149	.894	.768	1.041
Constant	1.107	.139	1	.000	3.025		
-2Log likelihood 14.513							

Ref., reference category; CI, confidence interval; Sig., significance *** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Women's likelihood to make household decisions in the realms of healthcare, mobility, household expenditures, and the utilization of funds earned by their husbands increases with advancing age. Notably, compared to women aged 15–19 (reference category), those aged 25–29 (OR=1.396, $p < 0.01$) had 1.4 times higher odds of participating in household decision-making. This indicates that decision-making autonomy increases with age. Rural women are 14% less likely to have decision-making autonomy than urban young women (OR=0.866, $p < 0.05$), suggesting geographical disparities in women's empowerment. Education plays a substantial role in enhancing decision-making autonomy. Women with higher education had 64% greater odds of participating in decision-making compared to women with no education (OR=1.641, $p < 0.01$). However, primary and secondary education did not show statistically significant effects.

Surprisingly, women from Scheduled Tribes had higher odds of decision-making (OR=1.173, $p < 0.05$), while those from 'Other' castes had significantly lower odds (OR=0.788, $p < 0.05$) compared to Scheduled Castes (SC). Working women had 1.5 times higher autonomy with those in non-agricultural occupations (OR=1.528, $p < 0.01$), and those in agriculture having 1.2 times higher odds (OR=1.257, $p < 0.01$), compared to non-working women. Exposure to mass media emerged as a significant and influential predictor. Women exposed to any one form of media had 31% higher odds (OR=1.306, $p < 0.01$), and those exposed to two or three forms had 46% higher odds (OR=1.458, $p < 0.01$) of decision-making autonomy. Marital duration was a strong predictor of household decision making power. Women had marital duration of 5–9 years (OR=1.255, $p < 0.01$) and 10–19 years (OR=1.290, $p < 0.01$) had significantly higher odds of decision-making compared to those marital duration of 0–4 years. A negative association was observed between women's decision-making autonomy and their husbands' level of education. Interestingly, women whose husbands consumed alcohol were 1.16 times more likely to have decision-making autonomy (OR=1.166, $p < 0.01$) compared to those whose husbands did not consume alcohol, a counterintuitive result that may reflect more complex household dynamics or stress-related responsibilities.

Negative husband attitudes towards wife-beating were associated with greater female autonomy. Women whose husbands had moderate (OR=0.894, $p < 0.05$) or low (OR=0.708, $p < 0.01$) justification for wife-beating were significantly less likely to experience limited decision-making, showing that more democratic attitudes of husband improve women's autonomy. Experience of any form of IPV was negatively associated with decision-making (OR=0.750, $p < 0.01$), indicating that violence undermines women's agency. Significant regional variations were observed with respect to women's independency on household decisions. Compared to the North, women in the Central, Eastern, North-Eastern, and Western regions had significantly higher odds of decision-

making, with the North-East showing the strongest association (OR=1.875, $p<0.01$). Women in the South did not differ significantly from those in the North.

The model highlights the multifaceted nature of women's decision-making autonomy in India, shaped by demographic, socio-economic, and cultural factors. Overall, binary logistic analysis reveals that factors such as a woman's age, education level, occupation status, employment status, and her husband's alcohol consumption behaviour significantly influence her likelihood of participating in household decision-making independently.

Discussion: The findings reveal significant variation in women's involvement in decision-making across different background characteristics, reinforcing the influence of structural and cultural factors on gender dynamics within Indian households. A key finding is the positive association between women's age and their participation in household decisions. This aligns with previous research showing that women's autonomy tends to increase with age due to greater experience and household influence (Bloom et al., 2001). Education emerged as one of the most powerful predictors of women's empowerment. Women with higher education were significantly more likely to participate in household decision-making compared to uneducated women. Prior studies support this, suggesting that education enhances women's awareness, self-confidence, and ability to negotiate (Jeejeebhoy, 1995; Acharya et al., 2010). Similarly, employment, especially in non-agricultural sectors, is positively associated with women's decision-making power, as it contributes to their economic independence and bargaining position (Kabeer, 2001; Kishor & Subaiya, 2008). Urban women report slightly higher involvement in decision-making than their rural counterparts, likely due to greater access to education, employment, and exposure to progressive gender norms in urban areas. However, the difference remains relatively small, suggesting that patriarchal norms persist across both settings (Desai & Andrist, 2010). Religious and caste-based disparities also influence decision-making patterns. Christian women showed the highest participation, while SC women reported lower levels of involvement. Similar patterns have been observed in earlier studies, where marginalized caste groups face dual disadvantages—both social exclusion and gender-based discrimination (Thorat & Newman, 2010; Singh et al., 2021). Exposure to mass media is significantly associated with greater decision-making autonomy among women. This finding is consistent with past research demonstrating that media plays a critical role in increasing awareness, changing gender attitudes, and promoting women's rights (Jensen & Oster, 2009; Dhawan, 2020). The attitudes and behaviors of husbands play a crucial role in shaping women's autonomy. Women whose husbands disapprove of wife-beating or who do not consume alcohol reported higher decision-making power. Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) was found to suppress women's autonomy, a finding echoed in previous research (Koenig et al., 2003; Abramsky et al., 2011), which highlights the detrimental effect of abusive relationships on women's agency and mental well-being. Regional variations are also evident, with women in the North-Eastern states showing higher participation. This may reflect more egalitarian norms prevalent in certain tribal and matrilineal communities (Deka & Kalita, 2017). In contrast, regions like Central and Southern India continue to exhibit lower levels of autonomy, possibly due to stronger adherence to patriarchal family structures. Interestingly, the wealth index did not emerge as a significant factor, indicating that economic well-being alone may not translate into

empowerment without corresponding shifts in social attitudes and gender norms (Sen, 1999).

Conclusion: The study underscores that promoting women's participation in household decisions requires a multidimensional approach. Enhancing educational and employment opportunities, addressing harmful gender norms, and promoting positive partner attitudes through awareness campaigns and policy interventions are essential. Addressing IPV and increasing mass media access can also serve as powerful tools to strengthen women's voices within the household. More specifically, the findings emphasize the critical need for inclusive educational initiatives, especially for women in rural areas, and culturally responsive, region-specific strategies to counter caste-based discrimination. These interventions should aim not only to raise awareness but also to empower women to assert their voices and choices within the household. By adopting such comprehensive and context-sensitive approaches, stakeholders can meaningfully contribute to the advancement of gender equity in India.

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